

OCEAN ICE News – December 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Festive Greetings!

Welcome to December's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, such as an OCEAN ICE publication, Polar Ocean Observations Map – GiF, highlighting October and December's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in January, February and March. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in January!

Merry Christmas and a Happy New Year!!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Zhetao Tan

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Zhetao Tan, a post-doctoral investigator in physical oceanography and operational oceanography at Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique – IPSL, Ecole Normale Supérieure — PSL in WP5.

Read the feature on Zhetao [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE Publication: Ocean warming threatens the viability of 60% of Antarctic ice shelves

A group of researchers from Grenoble, including OCEAN ICE participants, estimated dates, in given anthropogenic emission scenarios, beyond which individual ice shelves can no longer exist as they presently are. The authors took into account most uncertainties related to the future of the ice, atmosphere, and ocean, including deep uncertainties about poorly understood processes such as ice fracturing and calving.

In this study, the researchers took a step back and considered all the ocean atmosphere and ice processes that have the potential to change the mass of individual ice shelves. The fact that many aspects are poorly understood motivated the exploration of the full range of possibilities. This range was then reduced by giving more importance to the cases where the present-day estimates were close to observations. The authors also gave more importance to climate models simulating a plausible response to increased greenhouse gases. They had no confidence in their ability to estimate the evolution of a few key aspects like ice fracturing and calving. For these, they adopted a conservative approach, to be sure that their estimates remain valid regardless the future progress in the understanding of these processes. In the end, they were able to estimate dates beyond which there is high confidence that ice shelves can no longer exist in their current shape.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Exploring Polar Ocean Observations – GIF

Each point in this animation represents a different observing platform — with colours distinguishing between moored buoys, gliders, animal-borne instruments, ARGO profilers, CTD casts, and more.

What you see are the last recorded positions where each platform collected in situ data during that year. The dataset is drawn from sources available in SOOSmap (via EMODnet Physics).

See the Gif and catch up with the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – October

Climate Coffee with Blanca Fernández-Álvarez on How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean Marine Heatwaves

Oceans absorb most anthropogenic heat and a large share of carbon emissions, driving sea surface temperature (SST) increases and intensifying marine heatwaves (MHWs). Although rising MHW frequency is well documented, most studies rely on the standard fixed-baseline approach (Hobday et al., 2016), which uses a static climatology and is sensitive to long-term warming, thereby amplifying recent extremes and raising concerns about future MHW “saturation” (Rosselló et al., 2023). To address these issues, we compare three detection frameworks—fixed baseline (1982–2011), 20-year moving baseline (Rosselló et al., 2023), and a detrended method that removes the linear warming trend (Martínez et al., 2023)—across the Mediterranean Sea, a rapidly warming and ecologically vulnerable basin. Using SST data for 1982–2024, all three methods identify 2024 as the peak MHW year of the past two decades, with fixed and moving baselines also registering the longest-lasting events. Regionally, the eastern Mediterranean, where warming is strongest, recorded the most MHW days in 2024, whereas the western basin experienced exceptionally intense events in 2022. Depending on the detection framework, estimated MHW exposure across the Mediterranean can vary by up to fourfold. Fixed baselines remain useful for assessing thermal stress relative to historical conditions, while moving and detrended methods better track anomalies in a changing climate. Aligning detection frameworks with research and policy goals is therefore crucial for reliable climate risk assessment and regional adaptation planning. The research of this talk has been published on Ocean Science

<https://os.copernicus.org/articles/21/1987/2025/>

30 October 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Blanca Fernández-Álvarez (IMEDEA-CSIC)

How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean Marine Heatwaves

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – December

Climate Coffee with Ioannis Prapas and Haralampos Gavriilidis on Manteo AI: Making Earth Observation Workflows More Intuitive.

Working with Earth observation and remote sensing data is often a labour-intensive process. From identifying appropriate data sources and handling heterogeneous raster and vector formats to cleaning, transforming, and applying machine learning methods, each step requires significant expertise and

infrastructure. These hurdles can slow scientific progress and limit the accessibility of advanced geospatial analysis.

In this talk, we present the development of Manteo AI, a system designed to lower these barriers by integrating state-of-the-art research from data systems, remote sensing, and Earth observation, as well as artificial intelligence, particularly large language models. At its core, Manteo offers an interactive “chat map” interface, allowing practitioners to explore geospatial datasets through natural language queries and receive dynamic, visual responses in the form of maps, plots, and dashboards. As part of our roadmap, we also plan a community-driven model hub for Earth observation, where domain-specific models can be shared and seamlessly integrated into workflows. We invite practitioners to share their experiences and bottlenecks, so we can explore together how such cross-disciplinary methods might support more efficient and inclusive geospatial research.

Climate Coffee

11 December 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Ioannis Prapas and Haralampos Gavriilidis
(Manteo)

Manteo AI: Making Earth Observation
Workflows More Intuitive

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

OCEAN ICE represented at the Arctic Circle Assembly

OCEAN ICE is a part of The EU Polar Cluster who had a booth at the Arctic Circle Assembly in Iceland! OCEAN ICE gave the booth some flyers to advertise what the project researches!

From The EU polar Cluster:

There was a lot of interest in the EU funded polar research projects showcased at our booth; a very successful EU Polar Cluster evening networking session discussing four topics (ice, biodiversity, observations, and infrastructure) across disciplines and ages; and lots of interesting discussions with colleagues from all over the world.

It was also great to be positioned right next to the booth from Arctic PASSION!

Read the LinkedIn Post [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Earth Science and Climatology Winner Scanning Glaciers in the Antarctic Winter by Michael Meredith

Michael Meredith from OCEAN ICE has won the Publishing Photography Competition in the category of Earth Science and Climatology.

Read the Article from the Royal Society [here](#).

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in November and December, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Fehmi Dilmahamod on Characteristics of Mesoscale-to-Submesoscale Eddies in the Labrador Sea

29 January 2026, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

29 January 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online
Fehmi Dilmahamod (GEOMAR)
Characteristics of Mesoscale-to-Submesoscale Eddies in the Labrador Sea: Insights from Ship Observations

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by the European Union

Climate Coffee with Linus Vogt on Increased future ocean heat uptake constrained by Antarctic sea ice extent

19 February 2026, 15:00 – 15:45 (CET)

19 February 2026 | 15:00 - 15:45 CET
Online
Linus Vogt
(NYU, Sorbonne, LOCEAN)
Increased future ocean heat uptake constrained by Antarctic sea ice extent

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by the European Union

Climate Coffee with Giulia Bonino on Mediterranean summer marine heatwaves triggered by weaker winds under subtropical ridges

26 March 2026, 15:00 – 15:45 (CET)

26 March 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Giulia Bonino

(Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change)

**Mediterranean summer marine
heatwaves triggered by weaker winds
under subtropical ridges**

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

OCEAN ICE at Ocean Sciences Meeting

Members from OCEAN ICE will be presenting at the [Ocean Sciences Meeting in Glasgow, Scotland 2026](#). Please find the below talks during the meeting and look out for any future sessions/talks too:

David Chandler, Petra Langebroek, Heiko Goelzer, Michele Petrini and Morven Muilwijk.

Abstract ID: 2009920

Abstract Title: Global impacts of Greenland and Antarctic ice sheet freshwater fluxes in the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM)

Final Abstract Number: HE43A-09

Presentation Type: Oral

Session Number and Title: HE43A: Ice Sheet–Ocean Interactions: From Micro- to Climate-Scale II Oral

Session Date and Time: Thursday, 26 February 2026; 14:00 - 15:30 GMT

Presentation Time: 15:20 - 15:30 GMT

Location: SEC; Hall 3, Blue Horizon

Timothee Bourgeois, David Chandler, Michele Petrini, Elin Darelius, Petra Langebroek, Heiko Goelzer, and Jörg Schwinger.

Abstract ID: 2008310

Abstract Title: Committed Southern Ocean warming and implications for the Antarctic Ice Sheet following emission cessation

Presentation Type: Poster

Session Date and Time: Thursday, 26 February 2026; 16:00 - 18:00 GMT

Session Number and Title: HE44D: Variability, Circulation, and Ongoing Change in the Southern Ocean VI
Poster

Location: SEC; Hall 4 (Poster Hall)

Zhetao Tan:

Changing Properties of South Atlantic Upper-Ocean Water Masses During the Past 45 Years' in session PS21A - Atlantic Ocean Connectivity Across Latitudes: Large-Scale Processes, Observations, Modeling, and Impacts, which are targeted to the OCEAN ICE topic.

Session Date and Time: Tuesday, 24 February 2026, 09:23 - 09:33

Location: Hall 1 (SEC)

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 9th – 12th February 2026, [Open Science Conference](#), New Zealand
- 22nd – 27th February 2026, [Ocean Sciences Meeting](#), Glasgow, Scotland
- 9th – 13th March 2026, [CMIP 2026 Meeting](#), Kyoto, Japan
- 17th – 19th August 2026, [FRISP 2026](#), Kristineberg, Sweden

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

OCEAN:ICE

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452.